

**BACK PAIN: DEVELOPMENT OF ALGORITHMS FOR DIAGNOSIS
AND TREATMENT AT THE LEVEL OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE IN
THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: The causes of back pain can be degenerative-dystrophic changes in the spine and weakness of the musculoskeletal system that do not provide adequate resistance to load, damage to the nervous system (spinal cord, roots, peripheral nerves), pathology of the internal organs of the chest and abdominal cavity, pelvis, mental disorders in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: back pain, spinal pathology, diseases, diagnostic procedures

The most common cause of acute back pain is changes that occur when the muscles, ligaments, or joints of the spine are overloaded. Musculoskeletal causes of back pain are detected in 85-90% of patients. In most cases, they occur when performing "unprepared movement", may be associated with excessive load on the dugo-process joints of the vertebrae with degenerative-dystrophic changes in intervertebral discs. Such pain associated with musculoskeletal disorders without signs of damage to the spinal roots and serious spinal pathology, considered "non-specific" back pain (NS). Allocation of NS in Uzbekistan to a separate group is justified in most cases when the patient first goes to a General practitioner. Potentially dangerous causes of back pain associated with serious spinal diseases (primary and metastatic spinal tumors, spinal fractures in trauma and osteoporosis, spondylarthritis and infectious

lesions (tuberculosis, discitis), as well as diseases of the chest and abdominal cavity, pelvis and retroperitoneal space are referred to as "specific" back pain.

For back pain, a properly conducted clinical examination allows in most cases to clearly separate patients with specific and non-specific pain. First of all, when interviewing and examining a patient with back pain, the doctor should remember about "threat symptoms", the presence of which may indicate the possibility of a serious, sometimes life-threatening disease in the patient in Uzbekistan.

"Threat symptoms" that indicate the possibility of specific back pain include [1-19]:

- Onset of persistent back pain before the age of 15 and after the age of 50;
- Non-mechanical nature of pain (pain does not decrease at rest, in a lying position, in certain poses);
 - Association of pain with injury;
 - Gradual increase in pain;
 - History of cancer;
 - Occurrence of pain on the background of fever, weight loss;
 - Complaints of prolonged stiffness in the morning;
 - Symptoms of damage to the spinal cord and its roots (paralysis, pelvic disorders, sensitivity disorders);
 - changes in urine and blood tests.

If there are no "threat symptoms" during the initial examination, the patient is classified as having non-specific back pain, and he is prescribed analgesic therapy without additional diagnostic procedures. According to international standards, if a patient with back pain does not have "threat symptoms", it is not necessary to conduct laboratory and instrumental examinations, including radiography of the spine or CT and MRI studies [2]. It is important to remember that imaging methods with high frequency detect degenerative changes in the spine, even in patients without back pain. Thus, according to MRI of the lumbar spine, asymptomatic herniated discs are detected in persons less than 40 years of age in 30-40% of cases, and in persons over 60 years of age-in 100% [9, 21]. Degenerative-dystrophic changes in the spine, which are often

diagnosed by doctors as "osteochondrosis", can only be considered a prerequisite for the occurrence of back pain, but not its direct cause. The presence of signs of degenerative-dystrophic lesions of the spine tissues in patients with NBS in Uzbekistan does not correlate with the nature of pain or its intensity, so, despite the temptation to attribute radiologically detected signs of spinal osteochondrosis to the cause of pain, no convincing evidence of such a relationship has yet been obtained. In modern domestic and foreign guidelines for the diagnosis of back pain, x-ray examination is not a component of the primary examination [2].

Imaging methods and consultations with appropriate specialists are recommended for patients with back pain in unclear cases, when there are suspicions of a specific nature of the pain, which may be the result of a tumor, inflammatory or traumatic lesion of the spine, infectious processes, metabolic disorders, diseases of internal organs, muscle damage, damage to the nervous system, etc.

The presence of fever, local soreness in the par vertebral region is characteristic of infectious lesions of the spine. Its risk is increased in patients receiving immunosuppressive therapy, suffering from HIV infection, tuberculosis, and infectious diseases of the urinary tract. The causes of infectious complications can be recently transferred infectious diseases, tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, herpes zoster, spinal surgery, foci in the deep parts of soft tissues. Leucocytosis may be the only laboratory sign indicating a discitis or epidural abscess.

In half of all cases in patients with abdominal aortic aneurysm, the first symptom is back pain. Therefore, the presence of a pulsating volume formation in the abdomen during palpation is a serious reason for additional diagnostic procedures.

Compression fracture of the spine can be suspected in the presence of a spinal injury, as well as in persons with osteoporosis due to age-related disorders of calcium metabolism. Osteoporosis is most often detected in women in the post-menopausal period, in people taking glucocorticoids. Smoking, drinking alcohol and a sedentary lifestyle are also risk factors.

When examining the patient, it is important to pay attention to possible rashes on the skin, changes in posture, posture, gait, volume of movements in the spine, hip

joints, the degree of tension and soreness of the muscles, the localization of myofascial trigger points. At the same time, weakly expressed orthopedic symptoms in severe pain can be a sign of serious concomitant pathology. Neurological examination can detect damage to the roots and structures of the spinal cord.

Muscle-tonic pain syndrome occurs due to nociceptive impulses coming from the affected discs, ligaments and joints of the spine during static or dynamic overload. In more than half of cases, the source of nociceptive impulses is the arch-process (facet) joints, which is confirmed by the positive effect of blocks of the projection of these joints by local anesthetics. Nociceptors contained in cases of spinal roots, in the Dura mater, posterior and anterior longitudinal ligaments can also participate in the formation of pain. As a result of nociceptive impulses, reflex muscle tension occurs, which initially has a protective character and immobilizes the affected segment. However, in the future, the tonic tense muscle itself becomes a source of pain. In this case, areas of skin and muscle hyperalgesia, muscle tension, and restricted movement in the corresponding segment of the spine are detected. If you tilt in the anterior-posterior or lateral directions, the pain may increase. Pain relief is noted in the position of lying on your side with your legs bent at the knee and hip joints.

In complex therapy, it is also advisable to include physical therapy, reflexology, manual therapy (post isometric relaxation), and massage. As a rule, this combination of medication and non-medication methods of treatment helps to accelerate the recovery of patients with NS in Uzbekistan.

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